

ANTHONY MURMU

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Abstract: Anthony Murmu (1930-1985) witnesses to Jesus by awakening the Santals to their rights, accompanying them as their leader, and guiding them in their struggle for justice. As a Member of the Indian Parliament (1977-1980), he advances liberative political action and works tirelessly for their integral development. His unwavering commitment to securing their basic needs ultimately leads to his martyrdom in Banjhi on 19 April 1985. Through his dedication to social justice, the Adivasis grow in self-reliance and self-governance. His courageous witness continues to challenge us to engage responsibly in political life and to work steadfastly for justice.

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INTRODUCTION

This series, titled “GOSPEL in ACTION,” sheds light on Jesus’ witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the “pouring out of blood” (cf. Lk 22:20) testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹ Anthony Murmu (1930-1985) witnesses

¹ The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in the Series “GOSPEL in ACTION” in 2026 are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Kandhamal martyrs, Herman Rasschaert, Mathew Mannaparambil, Anthony Murmu, James Kottayil, Stan Swamy, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis. The *Acts of the Apostles* and *When the Gospel Grows Feet*, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title

to Jesus by conscientizing the Santal tribal community in Dumka-Raiganj, by accompanying them as their leader, and working for justice. As a member of the Indian Parliament (1977-1980), his legacy pivots around his liberative political action. With his life he pays the ultimate price for justice.

1. TRIBAL MARTYR FOR JUSTICE

Anthony Murmu is born in October 1930 at Durgapur village. He joins the Jesuits and is ordained a priest in 1967, the first Indian Jesuit for Dumka Raiganj Province (former Santal Mission). Soon after his ordination, he sets out to liberate his own Santal people and their land from *dikus* (exploitative non-Adivasis). The Santals consider him their messiah since he restores their land in a non-violent manner. He becomes a Member of Parliament (MP) in 1977 representing Rajmahal Lok Sabha constituency. His legacy is his work to legalize Adivasis' traditional self-governance system. On 19 April 1985 he is shot dead along with 14 other Santals by the landlord–moneylender–local administration *diku* nexus.²

The Home Minister, S. B. Chawan, informed the Lok Sabha on 23 April 1985 that “after taking all precautionary measures and finding no alternative to save life and property, Police had to fire twenty-five rounds in which 15 persons have been killed including Anthony Murmu, former Member of Parliament.”³

“GOSPEL in ACTion.” In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (1) a brief introduction to the martyr and their contextual Gospel praxis, and (2) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (*martyria*).

² This biographical profile of Anthony Murmu is adapted from the caption accompanying his photograph displayed at Bagaicha, a Jesuit-run training and social action centre in Ranchi. He was “the first Santal Jesuit of the Santal Mission.” Cf. V. M. Jose, *Towards a Local Tribal Church: An Anthropological and Missiological Exploration of the Jesuits among the Santals* (Pune: Jnana-Deepa – Christian World Imprints, 2021), 100.

³ Cf. Parliament of India, “Calling Attention to Matter of Urgent Public Importance: Reported Death of Many Adivasis and Injuries to Other as a Result of Firing by Police in Sahebganj District of Bihar,” https://eparlib.sansad.in/bitstream/123456789/819610/1/08_II_23-04-1985_p132_p146_PII.pdf (accessed on 12.03.2026).

As people's representative from Rajmahal, elected to the 6th Lok Sabha, Anthony Murmu has voiced for his people and has demanded justice for them. His parliamentary debates reveal that justice for Santals has been his utmost concern. He becomes the voice for his people through his reports in the Lok Sabha on starvation deaths among the Tribals and Dalits in Santal Parganas and through his demands for food, land, health, and other inalienable rights for them. Thirteen of his Lok Sabha interventions recorded between 31 March 1977 and 10 July 1979, and available on the Parliament Digital Library, testify to his firm commitment to Tribal welfare and justice.⁴

“As a grassroots social activist, he had the people's cause at heart. He had an ear to the ground. He was a born singer. Equipped with musical and composing talents, he organised a cultural troupe and conducted animation programs in villages. His popular techniques gathered crowds and they imbibed his messages. He was their ‘Murmu Baba.’”⁵ Santals from faraway villages used to come to Sahibganj to listen to him and to share their problems.⁶

⁴ Cf. Parliament Digital Library, “Exploring by Members Anthony Murmu,” <https://eparlib.sansad.in/browse?type=members&order=ASC&rpp=20&value=Anthony+Murmu> (accessed on 12.03.2026).

⁵ Cf. P. A. Chacko SJ, “The Blood of the Adivasi Martyrs,” *AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies* 66/3 (May-June 2021): 17. Chacko, at present the Director of Arrupe Tribal Cultural Centre in Sahibganj, has known Anthony Murmu personally. Based on his visit to the place of martyrdom on 20 April 1985, his meetings with the survivors of the firing, and on the sessions attended of the Enquiry Commission, he affirms that the report of PUCL after their inquiry “spared no words in pointing out the collusion between the police and the traders in exploiting the Adivasis. It also pointed out that the Enquiry Commission ordered by the Bihar government was a pre-planned ploy to suppress the truth and to give a lean chit to the administration and the business community.” Ibid.

⁶ George Beck SJ, spiritual director at Vidyajyoti, having worked with Anthony Murmu as a regent in Sahibganj during his Jesuit formation, recalls that many Santals used to come to “Murmu Baba” travelling even 15 kms. Beck remembers him vividly and affirms that he was extraordinarily intelligent. A visual biography (YouTube) identifies him as a contemporary of Shibu Soren and it reveals many other facts. Cf. “Politics : Fascinating Facts from Jharkhand's Lok Sabha

Murmu's oratorical skills and intellectual acumen have been at the service of such people. As a tribal leader and spokesperson of the Santals Anthony Murmu continues to fight for the rights of the Santals and to live in Banjhi, a Santal village in Jharkhand. He organizes them to demand justice from the administration. On 19 April 1985, a delegation led by him goes to meet the police. "On that day, he and 15 other Santals were killed in the police firing in Banjhi."⁷

The blood of Anthony Murmu and other martyrs has ignited a powerful movement among the Adivasis of the region, inspiring them to "free themselves from the clutches of money lenders and extortionists."⁸ Through a slow and steady process of conscientization, led by organizations such as the Sona Santal Samaj Samiti based in Kodma, the once victimized communities have reclaimed their land and laid to rest the oppressive moneylending system that dominated their lives. Today, the Adivasis of the area prioritize self-reliance through savings initiatives, cultivation of their own land, protection of forest resources, and self-governance through the provisions of the Panchayati Raj. Anthony Murmu's witness challenges all, especially Christians, to participate responsibly in political action.

2. JUSTICE (*MIŠPĀṬ*, *DIKAIOSYNĒ*)

In Jesus Christ, prophetic justice becomes incarnate justice. He is God's *mišpāṭ*⁹ walking among the poor.

Elections – Father Anthony Murmu," <https://youtu.be/QIO5rhFfKQ> (accessed on 16.03.2026).

⁷ Cf. Jose, *Towards a Local Tribal Church*, 101. Jose reports that Dumka Jesuits decided, after Murmu's murder, to carry on social action in Banjhi (shifted later to Kodma): "The Jesuit Regional Superior appointed Frs. Thomas Kavalakat SJ and Michael Raj SJ to Banjhi village for this uncharted work." *Ibid.*

⁸ Cf. Chacko SJ, "The Blood of the Adivasi Martyrs," 18.

⁹ *Mišpāṭ* (Hb) and *dikaiosynē* (Gk) are often translated as "justice." In the Hebrew Scripture, *mišpāṭ* signifies "what is right and proper, righteousness." Cf. B. Johnson, "*mišpāṭ*," *TDOT*, 9:92. Proper conduct is to be done in conformity with *mišpāṭ*, and it is "the God-given norm to ensure a well-ordered society." *Ibid.* It is the "universally binding norm of justice." *Ibid.*, 93. The Greek equivalent

Beginning his ministry with the prophetic justice agenda (cf. Lk 4:18-19 and Isa 61:1-2), i.e., “good news to the poor (*anawim*), release to captives, sight to the blind, freedom for the oppressed, and the year of the Lord’s favor,” he actualizes it. Just as prophetic justice protects the *anawim* of YHWH – the widows, orphans, and the migrants, he restores radically the socially excluded suffering from leprosy (cf. Lk 7:22), the marginalized women, morally excluded sinners, the economically oppressed poor, and the religiously excluded gentiles to their dignity. This is *mišpāṭ* in action. He stands in the line of Amos, Isaiah, and Jeremiah – speaking truth to power. Like the prophets, he confronts unjust power. Ultimately, he creates communities of justice.

The disciples continue Jesus’ *mišpāṭ* through *imitatio Christi* and their Spirit-guided praxis (cf. Acts 2:43ff; 4:32ff). Its climax is the Cross enacted as self-giving love. The resurrection is God’s “Yes” to Jesus’ *dikaioynē* and God’s “No” to the world’s justice. In continuity with Jesus’ Way, his witnesses today continue the prophetic justice that he embodies by restoring the marginalized, confronting oppressive systems (cf. Mk 11:15), forming a community of equality, and revealing that God’s justice is restorative love that heals and reconciles the world.

“The prophetic task of the Church is both constructive and critical and is exercised in the midst of a process of change.”¹⁰ In the Church’s tradition, “justice reflects a relational understanding of the self based on the principle of

for “justice,” *dikaioynē*, is “the observance of the will of God which is well-pleasing to Him.” Cf. Gottlob Schrenk, “*dikaioynē*,” *TDNT*, 2:196. It is “almost always used in the NT for the right conduct of [hu]man which follows the will of God and is pleasing to Him, for rectitude of life before God, for uprightness before His judgment.” *Ibid.*, 198.

¹⁰ Cf. Gustavo Gutiérrez, *A Theology of Liberation: History, Politics and Salvation*, trans. Caridad Inda and John Eagleson (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1973), 115-116.

the common unity of humanity.”¹¹ As a prophetic disciple of Jesus, Anthony Murmu engages in revolutionary processes for justice and the liberation of Santals and his creative political action bears fruits today through affirmative actions among the tribals.

CONCLUSION

Anthony Murmu’s life stands as a luminous witness to the Gospel enacted through courageous, restorative justice. In his struggle for the dignity and liberation of the Santals, he embodies the prophetic *mišpāṭ* of Jesus, confronting oppressive systems while nurturing communities of equality. His martyrdom reveals that authentic discipleship often demands costly love, yet it also unleashes transformative hope among the marginalized. His legacy summons Christians today to responsible political engagement that continues Jesus Christ’s justice as healing, reconciling action in the world.

¹¹ Cf. Paul J. Wadell, “Justice,” in *The Collegeville Pastoral Dictionary of Biblical Theology*, ed. Carroll Stuhlmueller (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1996), 517.